

Auxiliary materials for the paper ‘How context shapes the appropriateness of a robot’s voice’

Chi-square tables of the variables of interest in the study (robot voice gender, naturalness, accent, and context). First, a chi-square test was conducted on the whole contingency tables for each variable; then, the adjusted residuals for each cell were tested against a critical z value; this was the inverse normal distribution of the Bonferroni-corrected significance level.

TABLE I

NUMBER OF TIMES A ROBOT WAS SELECTED WHEN A FEMALE, MALE, OR AMBIGUOUS VOICE WAS PLAYED, IN THE 4 CONTEXT CONDITIONS, AND OVERALL, IN THE RV CONDITION. CHI-SQUARE RESIDUALS ARE IN PARENTHESIS. THE '***' INDICATES SIGNIFICANCE AT THE 95% LEVEL, AND THE '+***' INDICATES THAT THE TEST APPROACHES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. THE RESIDUALS ALSO SHOW THE DIRECTION OF THE PATTERNS: FOR EXAMPLE, THERE IS A POSITIVE, SIGNIFICANT ASSOCIATION BETWEEN FLASH AND THE MALE CATEGORY, MEANING THAT PEOPLE SELECTED FLASH MORE OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A MALE VOICE, AND LESS OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A FEMALE VOICE.

	Gender		
	Female	Male	Ambiguous
Flash			
Overall	20 (-3.81)***	58 (5.00)***	7 (-1.68)
Home	4 (-2.62)	17 (3.20)***	2 (-0.81)
Hospital	6 (-0.86)	11 (1.64)	1 (-1.11)
Restaurant	10 (-1.45)	20 (2.45)	2 (-1.42)
School	0 (-3.09)***	10 (2.92)+++	2 (0.24)
G5			
Overall	42 (0.67)	16 (-5.17)***	33 (6.36)***
Home	7 (0.08)	1 (-3.08)***	8 (4.25)***
Hospital	12 (-0.34)	6 (-2.74)	12 (4.36)***
Restaurant	9 (-0.38)	6 (-1.73)	8 (2.98)
School	14 (2.08)	3 (-2.93)+++	5 (1.20)
iCub			
Overall	65 (4.13)***	12 (-7.10)***	30 (4.36)***
Home	21 (2.84)	3 (-4.17)***	8 (1.89)
Hospital	10 (1.14)	0 (-3.85)***	8 (3.83)***
Restaurant	17 (2.27)	3 (-3.58)***	7 (1.86)
School	17 (1.66)	6 (-2.74)	7 (1.53)
Pepper			
Overall	97 (5.98)***	36 (-5.17)***	17 (-1.14)
Home	23 (3.20)***	6 (-3.26)***	5 (0.08)
Hospital	25 (2.45)	13 (-1.75)	4 (-0.99)
Restaurant	22 (2.82)	6 (-3.26)***	6 (0.61)
School	27 (3.51)***	11 (-2.19)	2 (-1.87)
Poli			
Overall	49 (1.03)	46 (0.40)	8 (-2.02)
Home	17 (1.66)	11 (-0.74)	2 (-1.29)
Hospital	13 (0.06)	15 (0.86)	2 (-1.29)
Restaurant	11 (0.72)	10 (0.26)	1 (-1.38)
School	8 (-0.47)	10 (0.47)	3 (0.00)
PR2			
Overall	24 (-5.61)***	92 (7.88)***	6 (-3.21)***
Home	2 (-3.64)***	21 (4.71)***	1 (-1.51)
Hospital	9 (-1.98)	23 (3.40)***	1 (-2.20)
Restaurant	5 (-2.61)	19 (3.33)***	2 (-1.03)
School	8 (-3.14)***	29 (4.43)***	2 (-1.82)
SCIPRR			
Overall	20 (-3.23)***	58 (5.91)***	0 (-3.79)***
Home	6 (-2.18)	20 (3.76)***	0 (-2.23)
Hospital	5 (-0.77)	10 (1.94)	0 (-1.64)
Restaurant	6 (-1.40)	15 (2.79)	0 (-1.98)
School	3 (-2.03)	13 (3.23)***	0 (-1.70)
Stevie			
Overall	31 (-0.38)	30 (-0.63)	15 (1.42)
Home	7 (-0.36)	8 (0.14)	3 (0.30)
Hospital	7 (-0.15)	9 (0.88)	1 (-1.03)
Restaurant	7 (-0.36)	8 (0.14)	3 (0.30)
School	10 (0.06)	5 (-2.17)	8 (2.98)+++

TABLE II

NUMBER OF TIMES A ROBOT WAS SELECTED WHEN A FEMALE OR MALE VOICE WAS PLAYED, IN THE 4 CONTEXT CONDITIONS, AND OVERALL, IN THE HV CONDITION. CHI-SQUARE RESIDUALS ARE IN PARENTHESIS. THE '***' INDICATES SIGNIFICANCE AT THE 95% LEVEL, AND THE '+++' INDICATES THAT THE TEST APPROACHES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. THE RESIDUALS ALSO SHOW THE DIRECTION OF THE PATTERNS: FOR EXAMPLE, THERE IS A POSITIVE, SIGNIFICANT ASSOCIATION BETWEEN FLASH AND THE MALE CATEGORY, MEANING THAT PEOPLE SELECTED FLASH MORE OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A MALE VOICE, AND LESS OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A FEMALE VOICE.

	Gender	
	Female	Male
Flash		
Overall	19 (-6.91)***	86 (6.91)***
Home	6 (-3.06)***	21 (3.06)***
Hospital	8 (-3.03)***	24 (3.03)***
Restaurant	2 (-3.88)***	19 (3.88)***
School	3 (-4.01)***	22 (4.01)***
G5		
Overall	89 (4.19)***	44 (-4.19)***
Home	24 (1.96)	13 (-1.96)
Hospital	15 (2.33)	5 (-2.33)
Restaurant	30 (2.47)+++	15 (-2.47)+++
School	20 (1.73)	11 (-1.73)
iCub		
Overall	83 (4.37)***	38 (-4.37)***
Home	26 (2.47)+++	12 (-2.47)+++
Hospital	21 (2.57)+++	8 (-2.57)+++
Restaurant	17 (1.67)	9 (-1.67)
School	19 (2.01)	9 (-2.01)
Pepper		
Overall	108 (5.85)***	42 (-5.85)***
Home	21 (2.34)	9 (-2.34)
Hospital	27 (2.82)+++	11 (-2.82)+++
Restaurant	29 (2.24)	16 (-2.14)
School	31 (4.46)***	6 (-4.46)***
Poli		
Overall	86 (4.61)***	38 (-4.61)***
Home	17 (1.67)	9 (-1.67)
Hospital	25 (1.92)	14 (-1.92)
Restaurant	20 (2.17)	9 (-2.17)
School	24 (3.50)***	6 (-3.50)***
PR2		
Overall	48 (-3.61)***	87 (3.61)***
Home	12 (-1.52)	20 (1.52)
Hospital	14 (-2.22)	27 (2.22)
Restaurant	14 (-0.58)	17 (0.58)
School	8 (-2.88)+++	23 (2.88)+++
SCIPRR		
Overall	31 (-3.47)***	63 (3.47)***
Home	9 (-0.89)	13 (0.89)
Hospital	6 (-1.47)	12 (1.47)
Restaurant	9 (-2.34)	21 (2.34)
School	7 (-2.15)	17 (2.15)
Stevie		
Overall	32 (-6.21)***	98 (6.21)***
Home	9 (-3.24)***	27 (3.24)***
Hospital	8 (-2.88)+++	23 (2.88)+++
Restaurant	3 (-3.42)***	18 (3.42)***
School	12 (-3.05)***	30 (3.05)***

TABLE III

NUMBER OF TIMES A ROBOT WAS SELECTED WHEN A NATURAL OR RESYNTHESED VOICE WAS PLAYED, IN THE 4 CONTEXT CONDITIONS, AND OVERALL, IN THE HV CONDITION. CHI-SQUARE RESIDUALS ARE IN PARENTHESIS. THE '***' INDICATES SIGNIFICANCE AT THE 95% LEVEL, AND THE '+++' INDICATES THAT THE TEST APPROACHES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. THE RESIDUALS ALSO SHOW THE DIRECTION OF THE PATTERNS: FOR EXAMPLE, THERE IS A POSITIVE, SIGNIFICANT ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PEPPER AND THE NATURAL CATEGORY, MEANING THAT PEOPLE SELECTED PEPPER MORE OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A NATURAL VOICE, AND LESS OFTEN WHEN THEY HEARD A RESYNTHESED VOICE.

	Naturalness	
	Natural	Resynthesised
Flash		
Overall	43 (-1.96)	62 (1.96)
Home	13 (-0.20)	14 (0.20)
Hospital	13 (-1.14)	19 (1.14)
Restaurant	6 (-2.05)	15 (2.05)
School	11 (-0.63)	14 (0.63)
G5		
Overall	66 (-0.09)	67 (0.09)
Home	16 (-0.89)	21 (0.89)
Hospital	11 (0.47)	9 (-0.47)
Restaurant	22 (-0.16)	23 (0.16)
School	17 (0.58)	14 (-0.58)
iCub		
Overall	88 (5.34)***	33 (-5.34)***
Home	31 (4.23)***	7 (-4.23)***
Hospital	21 (2.57)+++	8 (-2.57)+++
Restaurant	20 (2.90)+++	6 (-2.90)+++
School	16 (0.80)	12 (-0.80)
Pepper		
Overall	99 (4.25)***	51 (-4.25)***
Home	16 (0.39)	14 (-0.39)
Hospital	28 (3.17)***	10 (-3.17)***
Restaurant	34 (3.79)***	11 (-3.79)***
School	21 (0.89)	16 (-0.89)
Poli		
Overall	29 (-6.34)***	95 (6.34)***
Home	5 (-3.32)***	21 (3.32)***
Hospital	11 (-2.96)***	28 (2.96)***
Restaurant	6 (-3.36)***	23 (3.36)***
School	7 (-3.12)***	23 (3.12)***
PR2		
Overall	38 (-5.46)***	97 (5.46)***
Home	7 (-3.41)***	25 (3.41)***
Hospital	11 (-3.25)***	30 (3.25)***
Restaurant	8 (-2.88)+++	23 (2.88)+++
School	12 (-1.34)	19 (1.34)
SCIPRR		
Overall	46 (-0.22)	48 (0.22)
Home	12 (0.45)	10 (-0.45)
Hospital	9 (0.00)	9 (0.00)
Restaurant	13 (-0.78)	17 (0.78)
School	12 (0.00)	12 (0.00)
Stevie		
Overall	87 (4.14)***	43 (-4.14)***
Home	24 (2.16)	12 (-2.16)
Hospital	20 (1.73)	11 (-1.73)
Restaurant	15 (2.05)	6 (-2.05)
School	28 (2.37)	14 (-2.37)

TABLE IV

NUMBER OF TIMES A ROBOT WAS SELECTED WHEN AN AMERICAN OR IRISH ACCENT WAS PLAYED, IN THE 4 CONTEXT CONDITIONS, AND OVERALL, IN THE HV CONDITION. CHI-SQUARE RESIDUALS ARE IN PARENTHESIS. THE ‘***’ INDICATES SIGNIFICANCE AT THE 95% LEVEL, AND THE ‘+++’ INDICATES THAT THE TEST APPROACHES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. THE ONLY ASSOCIATION THAT APPROACHED SIGNIFICANCE WAS FOUND FOR *Stevie*, WHICH WAS SELECTED MORE OFTEN WHEN AN AMERICAN-ACCENTED VOICE WAS PLAYED, BUT ONLY IN THE RESTAURANT CONTEXT.

	Accent	
	Dublin	California
Flash		
Overall	54 (0.31)	51 (-0.31)
Home	13 (-0.20)	14 (0.20)
Hospital	14 (-0.76)	18 (0.76)
Restaurant	12 (0.68)	9 (-0.68)
School	15 (1.05)	10 (-1.05)
G5		
Overall	67 (0.09)	66 (-0.09)
Home	(-0.53)	20 (0.53)
Hospital	12 (0.93)	8 (-0.93)
Restaurant	27 (1.48)	18 (-1.48)
School	11 (-1.73)	20 (1.73)
iCub		
Overall	58 (-0.49)	63 (0.49)
Home	21 (0.71)	17 (-0.71)
Hospital	14 (-0.20)	15 (0.20)
Restaurant	10 (-1.24)	16 (1.24)
School	13 (-0.40)	15 (0.40)
Pepper		
Overall	71 (-0.71)	79 (0.71)
Home	15 (0.00)	15 (0.00)
Hospital	21 (0.71)	17 (-0.71)
Restaurant	19 (-1.15)	26 (1.15)
School	16 (-0.89)	21 (0.89)
Poli		
Overall	74 (2.30)	50 (-2.30)
Home	16 (1.24)	10 (-1.24)
Hospital	21 (0.52)	18 (-0.52)
Restaurant	17 (0.99)	12 (-0.99)
School	20 (1.95)	10 (-1.95)
PR2		
Overall	78 (1.94)	57 (-1.94)
Home	20 (1.52)	12 (-1.52)
Hospital	23 (0.85)	18 (-0.85)
Restaurant	19 (1.34)	12 (-1.34)
School	16 (0.19)	15 (-0.19)
SCIPRR		
Overall	43 (-0.87)	51 (0.87)
Home	9 (-0.89)	13 (0.89)
Hospital	7 (-0.98)	11 (0.98)
Restaurant	15 (0.00)	15 (0.00)
School	12 (0.00)	12 (0.00)
Stevie		
Overall	51 (-2.63)+++	79 (2.63)+++
Home	13 (-1.80)	23 (1.80)
Hospital	12 (-1.34)	19 (1.34)
Restaurant	5 (-2.51)+++	16 (2.51)+++
School	21 (0.00)	21 (0.00)